

Interview Transcript.

Daniel Alves, Elena Chestnova

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Introduction

The following interview was conducted in the context of the research project “ReSED API - Re-Use Standards for Editions Data with Application Programming Interfaces” funded by Swissuniversities in the period 01.07.2025 – 30.12.2026. Overall, ten interviews were conducted with the aim of consulting scholars who have detailed knowledge of the digital humanities and editions landscape to find out which data sharing and re-use practices they currently observe, and where the potential for broadening and deepening them lies.

The interviewee, in this case Prof. Dr. Daniel Alves from the New University of Lisbon, was sent a basic info questionnaire and a list of questions in preparation for a semi-structured interview which took place over video-chat. The transcript was generated by the integrated tool of MS Teams and edited by both participants of the interview. The publication of the transcript follows explicit consent given by the interviewee.

Chestnova Elena 0:04

CE

To start with, I'd like to ask you to say a few words about your institutional context and about your specialist interests, so that we know how to position what you're telling us.

Daniel Alves 0:30

OK, so my background is in history (bachelor, master and PhD) and my area of expertise is 19th-century history.

I'm a teacher and researcher at the New University of Lisbon in Portugal where I teach 19th century history, digital history and digital humanities. I coordinate a master in digital humanities and a lab that we have here, also in digital humanities, and I coordinate or participate in several research projects dealing with Open Access, research infrastructures and also related to digital humanities.

Chestnova Elena 1:32

CE

I assume that when you did your PhD on 19th century history, this was not yet in the digital. So what brought you to the digital world?

Daniel Alves 1:46

DA

No, it was. It was. I finished the bachelor in 1995 and then I started participating in projects that already used databases, geographic information systems and other technologies. I incorporated that in the master and also in the PhD. And of course when I finished the PhD in 2010, I was really much involved in the digital humanities movement.

Chestnova Elena 2:09

CE

And you said on the form [basic info questionnaire] that there is also a policy element to your work. What is that like?

Daniel Alves 2:30

DA

For four years finishing in July I was a member of the board of the of the School of Social Sciences and Humanities, one of the faculties of the New University of Lisbon. And in that position, I was responsible for digital transition and for digital humanities in the school. And I'm also now coordinating a project about the implementation and up-scaling skills on research data management, so more or less responsible with a team for guidelines, for tool-kits and for defining policies for research data management.

Chestnova Elena 3:25

CE

Starting on the focus of our interview, data reuse and specifically [digital] editions, data reuse and use of APIs.

You've said [on the basic info form] that you have reused the data of others, but so far as you know none of the data that you or your colleagues have produced has been reused. In what context have you been working with reused data?

Daniel Alves 3:57

DA

Well, usually data that is used by other researchers on their projects and that is shared with me in several ways. For instance, in geographic information systems. We usually reuse a lot of shapefiles, a lot of statistical information that usually is available from other projects, for instance from environmental studies, we usually use some of those in history projects. And data that's made available in some publications, for instance, data about railways in Portugal that was collected from different projects and then we made a study integrating some of the data for long series studies of the building of the railways in Portugal since the middle of the 19th century until the present time.

Chestnova Elena 5:40

CE

Do you find that in the area where you're active as a researcher, it's common practice to reuse data and also to share the data for reuse?

Daniel Alves 5:50

DA

No, but well, in the digital humanities fields it is common, but not in history, in traditional research in history it is not at all that common.

I think probably in my field it is more common because I also do a lot of work with quantitative data and quantitative history. I use a lot of census data, migration data, railways data, prices, and so on and so forth. And for that I usually reuse data that was already collected by others. But usually it's not something that in the field of history people do here in Portugal, at least on a large scale.

Chestnova Elena 6:45

CE

Why do you think that is? Is there hesitation about the whole practice of reuse? Or is there a lack of understanding about what constitutes data in this field?

Daniel Alves 7:01

DA

Yes, I think most of the researchers don't think of the information, the historical sources, as data. There are sources that they use. Usually they don't publish the full spectrum of sources

that they collect, they only publish a selection of it or the results of the analysis on those sources. Although there are of course projects that are committed, but in that case they are really committed to publish the sources.

But no, I don't think that most of them think of it as data to be reused, to be published so that people can use the data to publish other research. Not in the way that we in the digital humanities field think of data for reuse.

Chestnova Elena 8:20

CE

You mentioned that you're also involved with data management training. I assume in that aspect of your work you have to do with people from different disciplines. Do you feel that there is more or less openness towards this idea of making data open, reusing data, allowing the reuse of data and so on?

Daniel Alves 8:44

DA

Well, mainly I deal with people from social sciences and humanities inside these two projects that I'm participating in this year. They are one-year projects only. I got in contact with people from mathematics, engineering, IT. I think in those areas, biology, for instance, or medical biology, in those areas, it's more common - at least from the point of view that I'm in when we participate in the meetings and so on - I think it's more common for them to have a clear notion what is data, what is research data and how it can be reused and how they can reuse that data. It's not all that common in the social sciences, and less even in the humanities. So that's my understanding.

Chestnova Elena 10:07

CE

Do you feel that the researchers you work with from those fields would benefit from greater reflection, let's say, on what is data, how it can be re-used and shared?

Daniel Alves 10:08

DA

For sure. For sure. That's why we committed here, in the School of Social Science and Humanities, to participate in these two projects. We are in the national consortium that's running a lot of initiatives to get people thinking about these topics and to give them skills, to upgrade them in skills, with good skills, with good guidelines, good tools so they can start implementing that. I'm also involved in a competence center that aims to foster education and training for research data management, so that people know what is data, know what is research data, know how to implement a research data management plan for instance, where to put the data at the end of the project, how to track the usability of the data.

Chestnova Elena 11:36

CE

And when you've reused other people's data, do you feel that it came in a reasonably reuse-friendly form? Was it well documented? Where the formats something that is commonly used, where they open and so on? Or did you feel that you had to do a lot of work to reuse data made by others in your field?

DA Daniel Alves 12:03

In my personal experience, I don't think that it was all that difficult. As for documentation, I think it was better when I started reusing data from the geography field and from environmental studies field because that type of data usually came with documentation, because we need to know the coordinate systems, we need to know the way that data was captured so we can integrate in our own projects. But data coming from other fields, say from literature or history... Well the data is available and I was able to reuse it quite easily but most of the time there was no documentation about it. And sometimes there was a need for some transformation or cleaning of the data so that it can be reusable.

CE Chestnova Elena 13:13

And when you worked with data from the field of literature - because obviously our project is coming from the editions perspective and we're really trying to talk to the editions people - how did you find that? What sorts of data did you reuse? How did that go, broadly speaking? I assume this was also editions in a very broad sense of somebody who's digitized some kind of text and published it online.

DA Daniel Alves 13:37

Yes, in most of the cases it was digitized text from novels in Portuguese literature, for instance, and the same with histories and some texts that were published, but in case of history mainly quantitative data that I reuse. In the case of literature it was essentially the data that was used or novels that were already digitized and OCRed for other projects and then we reuse that in our projects also. I'm trying to think about other possible corpus of analysis, but no, that's mainly about it.

CE Chestnova Elena 14:35

Was this coming from an existing literary corpus that's published formally online, or was this coming from different sorts of sources that you had to compile together and harmonize?

DA Daniel Alves 14:53

The works came from different origins, but mainly projects that are already online. One of them was from Oslo for instance, that had a large project of digitizing and making available literature in Portuguese. And the others, well... For instance Gutenberg project and others, and there was also a project in Brazil that already made a lot of Portuguese-speaking literature available online that was outside the authors rights, so we could reuse them.

CE Chestnova Elena 15:43

In what form was this? Did you e-mail the Oslo colleagues and they just sent you a dump of data? Or did they have XML files you could download, or did you just have to take plain text?

DA Daniel Alves 15:52

No, no. Plain text, or in some cases only PDFs. But in most of the cases it was possible to

download plain text, which is of course a format more interoperable and more easy to be reused.

But mainly those two types, not XML because we did not have the need to use that structured data for the work that we did.

Chestnova Elena 16:20

CE

And did you feel at the time that a slightly different way of presenting the data or exposing the data would have been more useful for your work? Or was it enough for you to just have this pile of text and PDF plain text and you could work with that?

Daniel Alves 16:48

DA

Well, from the perspective of the project that I was working on at the time, it was clearly enough. There was no need for having another type of structured data or, I don't know, the type of access to that data posed no problem for us. We could use the data as it was, so it was easy for the type of work that we did. Although now I supervise a researcher here for two years who was here in the lab and the project was to make digital editions of authors from South America from the beginning of the 20th century and the work that she has done made me realise that probably if we had access to that type of data when we started many years ago with this project on literature, it would have been much easier for us to work because the data is structured, it's presented in multiple formats, it's interoperable, it's already annotated. So, it will be a lot easier to reuse.

Chestnova Elena 18:02

CE

Moving on to the question of APIs, one of the motivations that led into this project was that I lead a large digital edition and as part of this, we put online a little API that we coded in GraphQL. It was not a large amount of work and since then we've been going around saying hello, we have this API, please use our data. What would you like the API to do? And there was sort of a big silence coming back with a slight element of confusion because there isn't really a knowledge about APIs or an expectation of what an API is supposed to do, what you can do with it and so on. So part of our project now is to conduct some training around APIs and bring the community together to propose a set of recommendations around data reusing and APIs. And part of it are these interviews to try and take the temperature a little bit of the digital humanities community around the question of APIs.

You said [on the basic info form] that you've both used and set up APIs. What was that like?

Daniel Alves 19:21

DA

Well, I interact with APIs in the frame of the project that is still running. It is an infrastructure for aggregating cultural heritage data. We get access to APIs or interoperable protocols that allow us to aggregate data from museums, libraries, archives, but not from the research field. In the area of academic research it was very difficult for us to incorporate data and to aggregate data from projects that deal with Portuguese-speaking cultural heritage. It was a lot easier to aggregate data through APIs or through the OAI protocol and to integrate data that came from the cultural heritage institutions, then from the research community, from our research units. For instance, we have knowledge of a lot of databases, a lot of platforms, a

lot of websites that publish results of projects related to the field and that it could be useful for the project to incorporate. But in most cases it was not possible, essentially because people don't know or people didn't have time to implement an API or it was not an issue for them, it was not something relevant for them. There is a long history of publication of data online but then it's closed. It's there, but it's very difficult to reuse. And it was interesting to see that the cultural institutions are more or less ready for this. The research community, at least from the field of humanities, is not ready for this. Yet.

Chestnova Elena 21:47

CE

What do you think fuels this lack of interest? Is there absence of incentives or is there kind of just complete unconcern for whether the data gets reused or not, or is there kind of proprietary attitude?

Daniel Alves 22:04

DA

No, no, no. I think most of my colleagues, when they publish the results of their projects online and when they publish the data in several formats online, they are expecting people to use and reuse the data. But I don't know if it's because of difficulties on the technical side, because it was not mandatory or it was too expensive to build an API or something like that. Or simply because they ignored that just putting data online does not provide an easy way for people to reuse that data in the same sense that the project did. Because with most of the databases we can only access the data when we launch a query to the database and we cannot extract the data easily from the database so we can reuse it. But I think most of my colleagues ignore this. It's not a concern for them. They already published the data and they think, well, the data is out there, people can reuse it. But no, it's not usable.

Chestnova Elena 23:32

CE

And from the side of institutions or funders in Portugal, there is also no incentive to try and drive this forward to get better value out of this data?

Daniel Alves 23:46

DA

Now I think there is in the funding that we get for this one-year project. Before that there was an initiative to make a pilot project building a research data repository in Portugal, because we don't have a national research data repository yet. And now when I think two or three years back, I think there is more interest and more concern about it. It is still not a mandatory policy, but I think it probably will be next year or the year after. So that projects will only be funded when they adhere to FAIR principles and to sharing the data according to FAIR principles. It's not mandatory yet but these initiatives that provide funding to raise awareness and skills in the field, they are an indication that in the near future it will be.

Chestnova Elena 25:01

CE

You've mentioned that your colleagues have interesting data, it's published, but it's not very findable. Are there other aspects that make it difficult to reuse data apart from findability and access?

Daniel Alves 25:20

DA

Probably the formats, and where and how the data is published. Usually, it's published on relational databases or platforms that don't have interfaces where people can download the whole data set easily for instance. Here in the lab that I coordinate, we try to put data and results of the projects on platforms that at least allow people to download all the data in CSV files for instance, which is, well, it's not perfect, but at least it's something that people can do. We also integrate interoperable protocols in platforms like Omeka, Tainacan, Drupal where people can download the data manually or via machines or algorithms. It can be downloaded, but it's not common, at least in this field, it's not common.

Chestnova Elena 26:39

CE

And when you used APIs yourself for your own research, what sorts of APIs were these? And what was easy, what was not so easy?

Daniel Alves 27:00

DA

Well, personally... Apart from the work that we have done inside the ROSSIO infrastructure - that research infrastructure that I was talking about - I don't recall if I ever used APIs. Well, again, probably in the field of geographic information system. Yes, because the geographic information system software has incorporated some features that can allow us to contact with APIs, then we can ask things to the interface and collect data. Mainly in that topic and with that type of data. Not in history, I don't recall using an API for collecting data in history, not in the sense of what we are understanding as a proper API. Probably a website where the data was more accessible and more easy to download, but not an API.

Chestnova Elena 28:31

CE

Also not for things like newspapers or images and so on?

Daniel Alves 28:41

DA

Well, there are of course databases, because we have the National Library and some of the newspapers are available in digital format. In Brazil, there is a lot of data from the 19th century also because in our work we also take data from there that is available. But not as API, at least as I recall...

Well, there was a colleague that was working with us in the lab for one year that accessed an API, I think from the National Library in Brazil, where he collected data from newspapers. But apart from that, I was not directly involved. I was supervising this work, but I was not directly involved in the work. But as I recall, probably is the only one. For the other sources, we have traditional catalogues or traditional databases where we search, get results and in the end we can download the data if that option is available, but not query an API.

Chestnova Elena 30:01

CE

Do you think it would be helpful in your work if APIs were more common?

DA Daniel Alves 30:10
Of course, a lot, a lot. *[laughs]*

CE Chestnova Elena 30:12
In what aspects?

DA Daniel Alves 30:29
For instance, sometimes the data is updated or there is a new data set that is made available, is corrected or something like that. If we could dynamically interact with the APIs, we could have this type of data updated or at least have a notion that there is more data available, that we could download it.
Again, in the field of geographic information systems, there has been a lot of work done over many years, so it's possible to keep up with the data and to use it.
For history, there is not. There is nothing. In most of the cases there is not. So, data is difficult to access most of the times not in the format that we can easily reuse, not organised in a structured way. At least in those features it would be quite helpful if we have access to that, yeah.

CE Chestnova Elena 31:25
What other aspects of that data make it difficult to reuse? Also, you said it's not organised and that makes it hard to reuse. What other things are there? Is it documented? Is it structured?

DA Daniel Alves 31:49
Most of the time no. Most of the time it's not documented, at least in the history field it's not properly documented. So we can see that in most of the of the cases when we start exploring a database, we don't know how many items there are in the database, for instance, or what type of fields the data is organised in. Most of the times the fields are not mapped to a proper metadata scheme, for instance Dublin core or something like that. So it makes it harder for us to reuse.
Or in other cases, we can download the data that is structured, but the names of the fields are a complete mystery for us. What does it mean? A field called "1234" or something like that? *[laughs]*

CE Chestnova Elena 32:47
[laughs]

DA Daniel Alves 32:54
So it's very, very difficult to use this type of data. I recall for instance a project that I was involved in many years ago about the publication of a census from the former colonies in Africa. It was a project about the demography of those colonies in the 19th century. The data was published in Excel files that people could download, but the names of the fields were only comprehensible to the people that worked with the files. So OK, the data is there, but

we need to do extra work, go an extra mile to comprehend the data and how it's organised. Probably it's my experience from the Portuguese point of view, but I don't know. I think in other countries the experience is different.

Chestnova Elena 33:56

CE

I don't think it's that different. Actually, based on the interviews I've done so far, the kinds of problems that people describe are fairly similar.

And so talking of problems, what do you think would help the humanities in general, and perhaps your specialist field in history, to move forwards on these issues? Does there need to be incentive from the government and funders, or does there need to be more education, or?

Daniel Alves 34:24

DA

Yeah, I think so. Training. We need to incorporate these issues early in the education of the students in the bachelor. Usually most of the researchers only get a notion about these topics and what they need to do with the data and so on and so forth when they finished the PhD, because at that stage they start to be able to apply for research funding for individual projects and then the funding agencies start asking them, well, what about data management plans? What about Open Access? What about publishing the data in open repositories? And most of them don't know anything about it. So we need to start teaching our students also in the beginning, so that at least when they get in contact with that, they have the knowledge. So that's one of the things, training, and incorporating, I don't know, at least a module in some course about these issues. I do that with my history students because I talk with them about Open Access, about FAIR principles, about data management briefly, of course in three or four classes only, but at least it's something that will stay with them when they hear about it. Afterwards, at least they recognise the topic and they can say something about it.

And of course incentives from the government because in a project we are usually funded to make research not to deal with data, not to manage data; and probably the funding agencies need to incorporate a specific type of budget for this so we can hire people that are experts in data management. My goal is not to be an expert on data management. My goal is to be an expert on historical research, so probably more funding for more openness to hire people that are not directly connected to the research but are connected to other tasks that are also important at the end of the project for the usability of the data. We need a change of policy on that.

Chestnova Elena 37:44

CE

I think we've actually covered all of the questions that I've put down for these interviews. Are there any other points [of discussion] that I haven't brought up and that you would like to talk about?

Daniel Alves 37:55

DA

No, no, I don't think so.